

Utilizing a high-throughput microdevice to study breast tumor cells clustering and metastasis

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(Supporting information)

Figure. S1. Scheme of the photolithography procedures.

Fig S2. The design of AG-chip. (A) Schematic of the layers that are assembled during device fabrication. (B) There are multiple 10×10 microwells array on chip. Scale bar, $200 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig S3. The cell loading of AG-chip. (A) Cell loading with the cell suspension of 5×10^4 cells/ml. Scale bar, 200 μm . (B) The number of cells in the microwells were varied at different cell density in the loaded cell suspension. (C) Distribution of cell numbers when the loaded cell suspension is diluted to 5×10^4 cells/ml.

Figure. S4. Surface treatment of the devices. BME treatment (Top) results in an adherent culture while PEG5000 treatment (Bottom) results in a suspension culture. Scale bar, 100 μm .